

Working Paper

Diffusion agents and institutional change: the variable influence of independent regulatory agencies within regulatory arrangements across sectors in India

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to explore variations in the influence of IRAs in regulatory arrangements beyond functional explanations, focusing on six sectors in India. This article maps regulatory arrangements in India using measures of concentration, and coordination to assess actor influence. We observe a correlation between nature of diffusion agents and variable influence of IRAs within the regulatory arrangement. To investigate this correlation, research on channels of transfer is juxtaposed with a theory of institutional change. Channels of transfer can induce a type of institutional change that can contribute to explaining variations in the influence of IRAs within regulatory arrangements. Our findings corroborate these expectations. For electricity, a sector strongly exposed to diffusion agents, the formal regulatory arrangement shows IRA as the most influential actor, whereas in the telecommunications sector, the pre-existing governmental actor has managed to retain the influence despite setting up an IRA.

Key Words: regulatory arrangement, channels of transfer, institutional change, India

1. Introduction

Regulation can be a curious concept. Like the idiom of 'the blind men and an elephant', the understanding of regulation seems to have been shaped, as Koop & Lodge suggests, by disciplinary differences. In its narrowest sense, much traditional regulation is understood as 'command-and-control' (CAC) by the state. In its broadest sense, it can be understood as an intervention that is intentional and direct, and exercised by public actors over private actors (Koop & Lodge 2017). Black's broader conceptualization of decentered regulation envisages intentional interference that can be exercised by both public and private actors (Black 2002). Regulatory governance, as a discipline, is about the study of political and policy processes of making and implementing regulation, encompassing varied understandings of its purpose and role.

In the study of regulatory governance, Independent Regulatory Agencies (IRAs) are the main protagonist. These agencies, which would operate at an arm's length from ministries, diffused across geographies and inserted themselves in the pre-existing institutional setting and manifested in shape and form that was either consistent or different from the administrative system of the country. Bianculli et al's (2013) dataset on de jure institutional characteristics suggests how countries with varied administrative traditions have adapted the institutional model of regulatory agencies. Though IRAs are tasked with regulation, sectoral oversight is undertaken not by one but many actors resulting in what can be termed as constellation or arrangement of actors (Mathieu et al. 2016; Jordana & Sancho 2004).

Jordana & Sancho's (2004) work emphasized the need to study institutional constellations (the entire set of formal institutions and interconnected rules that shape decision-making), arguing that the new actor, i.e. IRA, is embedded into an institutional setting that would exert its influence. While analyzing differences in the institutional guarantee of independence in telecommunications and electricity sectors in Brazil, influence of other actors, such as bureaucracy, judiciary, and politicians was observed on the institutional design post regulatory reforms (Prado 2012). The study, measuring and comparing the distribution of decision-making power in the regulatory arrangement of telecommunications sector across four Latin American countries, found variations not only at sector level but also at the level where regulatory issues were divided into economic, technical, and social regulation (González 2017). These instances suggest there is a need to study macro-level design.

There is literature that has studied diffusion and IRAs. The focus on the regulatory arrangement is a relatively new development in the field of regulatory governance as it examines the complex web of actors whose interventions and interactions sustain the regulatory process in a given policy field (Mathieu et al. 2016). Though these concepts have been studied independently, they are also inter-linked. Diffusion is a process whereby diffusion agents insert IRAs (micro-unit) into the regulatory arrangement (macro-unit). As it adds to a pre-existing set up (and also different administrative set-up), there is a possibility that dispersion of power and influence among actors will vary. To explore this aspect, this paper, examines correlations between diffusion agents and regulatory arrangements (including IRAs).

We suggest that to understand institutional outcomes, attention should be paid to the dynamics of adoption including the role of intermediating agencies that act as a vector for the various channels of diffusion (Dubash 2012). The objective of this study is to identify how the configuration of formal regulatory arrangements in any given sector and country case, in particular the influence of IRAs, derives from the nature of diffusion agents (exogenous or endogenous). The diffusion of regulatory institutions did not happen in a vacuum; rather this new form of administrative regulation diffused through an agent and produced an outcome. The idea is to gauge the variation in the influence of IRAs in the institutional outcome that was produced by diffusion.

Diffusion is defined as *“the process whereby information on the creation of new institutions is communicated through certain channels over time among the members of a social system in an uncoordinated manner, and prior adoptions of an innovation affect the probability of adoption for some of the remaining non-adopters in the population”* (Jordana et al. 2011). The authors in their paper separate diffusion as a process from the outcomes that it may or may not produce. Building onto their work this paper moves beyond the process and explores what outcome diffusion produced. When the channels of institutional transfer as presented by Jordana et al (2011) are complemented by the diffusion literature from the developing economies, two types of diffusion agents emerge: exogenous and endogenous. The mode of institutional change that these agents induce is different as a result of which there are divergences in the formal regulatory arrangements across sectors within the same country.

From the literature, it is known that actors do not operate in isolation. In any policymaking or regulatory decision-making process, many actors interact with each other. The notion of regulatory space suggests that resources are fragmented among the actors, and thus the

potential influence. This reinforces the idea that the role of agencies and the interaction between involved actors can adopt multiple configurations. The concept of regulatory arrangement helps in classifying the possible configurations these macro-structures can take.

India was chosen as a case for analysis because a large number of agencies have been created, including at the state level, and significant variation merits further scrutiny. In addition, there had been attempts to undertake regulatory reform. Two reports, one by the erstwhile Planning Commission of India (now NITI Aayog) in 2006 “Approach to Regulation: Issues & Options” and the other by the second administrative reforms commission (ARC) constituted by Government of India in 2009, both recognized the absence of a common regulatory philosophy as there was inconsistency with respect to the powers and functions of the regulators, independence of these regulatory agencies, lack of uniformity in appointment and removal of members, etc. (Moily et al., 2009; Planning Commission 2006). To overcome the absence of common regulatory philosophy and to guide the next stage of regulatory reform, the Planning Commission of India proposed a Regulatory Reform bill in 2013 (yet to be passed), an overarching law to govern institutional framework of IRAs for public utilities.

This proposed regulatory reform aims to rationalize the power and functions of IRAs. However, this renegotiation of regulatory space should be done with consideration of the entire sectoral arrangement as the capacities of actors will be enhanced or constrained (Scott 2001). A prerequisite for this consideration would be to know how the sectoral arrangement looks like. This study undertakes the mapping of the formal regulatory arrangements of a few sectors in India to explore their sectoral configuration and influence of IRAs vis-à-vis other actors.

The question guiding this research is:

RQ: In the landscape of regulatory governance in India, a) how diverse are the regulatory arrangements of the sectors where IRAs exist, and b) can agents of diffusion explain variations in the regulatory arrangements and influence of IRAs in each sector?

The study explores the relationship between nature of diffusion agents and resultant formal regulatory arrangement by complementing Jordana, Levi-Faur & Marin’s work on global diffusion of regulatory agencies with Mahoney & Kathleen’s theory of gradual institutional change. Our findings supplement two areas of literature; one deals specifically with IRAs and

their institutional design and the other deals with the analysis of regulatory arrangements per se in Europe and Latin America.

Following this introduction, section two of this article discusses the theoretical framework and hypothesis. Section three explains the methodology. Section four presents the findings and section five discusses those findings. Section six concludes the paper.

2. Theoretical framework

This study draws on the theory and concepts of diffusion agents and regulatory arrangements. Diffusion is a process and diffusion agents are the carriers involved in the process. The regulatory arrangement is shaped by the process of institutional change.

2.1 Diffusion and diffusion agents

The genesis of an agency that would comprise of non-partisan experts tasked with certain responsibilities can be traced to the nineteenth century United States (USA) (namely, the creation of the Interstate Commerce Commission). With the burgeoning of the economy during the early twentieth century, this non-partisan body of experts evolved as an independent regulatory agency (IRA) after being accepted as an organizational form in the administrative framework of USA (Breger and Edles 2015; Pandey 2018). After attaining acceptance and popularity in the United States, IRAs diffused to Europe in the post-war era. The spread of the American philosophy of regulation, that is, the growth of administrative regulation, altered the nature of European states from service providers to regulators (Majone 1997). Majone conceptualized the growth of administrative regulation in Europe as the rise of the regulatory state.

At the heart of Majone's regulatory state was the IRA, an institutional development with a high functional value. Accordingly, this new institution, which would operate at an arm's length from the ministerial bodies, was brought to the developing economies where financial assistance was provided by the multilateral institutions, such as the World Bank (WB) and the International Monetary Fund (IMF). Numerous studies have been undertaken on the diffusion of IRAs across the globe. Jordana et al (2011) observed that the process of regulatory agencification exploded globally from the 1990s to 2002 (Jordana et al. 2011).

It is well documented that in this interconnected world, ideas travel, but they need a medium. Based on the functional value argument, the idea that the regulatory agencies are a 'best-practice' measure emerged and diffused through various channels. Jordana et al (2011) in their study of diffusion identified two primary channels of institutional transfer: National Patterns Approach (NPA) and Policy Sector Approach (PSA).

According to the National Patterns Approach (NPA), the diffusion of regulatory agencies occurs pre-dominantly through national political networks. The national community of policymakers, who are the drivers of policy change, make institutional changes in their own country by formulating policies to establish regulatory agencies, leading to their diffusion. The NPA further consists of National Transfer (NT) and International Transfer (INT) channel. In the former channel, policymakers adapt regulatory agencies to diverse sectors within the country, whereas in the latter regulatory agencies are established after policymakers learn from experiences of the other countries. The Policy Sector Approach (PSA) emphasizes the existence of multiple political networks that lead to the diffusion of regulatory agencies. The national community of policymakers are not the drivers of policy change, rather they are influenced by external factors to make policy change. PSA also consists of two sub-channels: Sector Transfer (ST) and Intersectoral Transfer (IST). For example, the creation of electricity regulatory agencies in one country leads to the diffusion of electricity regulatory agencies in other countries. Similarly, an instance of intersectoral transfer shows how the establishment of telecommunications regulatory agencies influenced the creation of electricity regulatory agencies (Jordana et al. 2011).

In India, independent regulatory agencies (IRAs) were adopted in the aftermath of the 1991 economic crisis. This crisis led to a paradigm shift in economic policy as India embarked on the path of neoliberalism. From 1991 onwards, IRAs have been established in many sectors such as securities, telecommunications, electricity, insurance, real estate etc. The literature on diffusion of regulatory agencies in India suggests that as the government turned towards multilateral institutions during the Balance of Payment (BOP) crisis in 1991, it led to India becoming a part of a third wave to adopt the model of regulatory institutions (Arora 2018; Dubash and Morgan 2011; Dubash and Singh 2005).

Dubash (2001, 2005, 2012), in numerous works, has extensively analyzed the diffusion of regulatory agencies in India. By tracing the reform story of the electricity sector, he argues that in developing countries like India, the regulatory agencies were brought about by the

multilateral donor agencies (such as the World Bank and International Monetary Fund) on the pretext of depoliticizing the sector (Dubash 2012; Dubash and Rajan, 2001; Dubash and Singh, 2005). A similar opinion was echoed by others who have analyzed reform in the power sector (or water sector) that the institution of IRA was transplanted in India by an external actor (Mukherji 2004; Thiruvengadam 2016; Warghade 2016).

Contrasting the view that IRAs were established solely by an external actor, an analysis of the telecommunications sector concluded that the need for an IRA gestated over a period of time within the political and bureaucratic elites; when the opportune moment came, the reforms were driven by a national community of policymakers (Mukherji 2006, 2009, 2014). Mukherji's argument of endogenously driven change is further supported by an analysis of reforms in India's securities market, seconding the idea that India's securities market requires endogenously driven institutional change (Echeverri-Gent 2007).

The channels of diffusion provide pathways (NPA & PSA) through which diffusion can happen, but it does not provide the agents who follow these paths of diffusion (Dubash 2012). To explore the diffusion process, it is important to locate agents that follow those paths to create institutional change. From the above-mentioned examples from India, two kinds of diffusion agents can be identified based on whether agents are from outside or from within a country's national political network. By considering channels of transfer and diffusion in India, we deduce that diffusion can be attributed to two types of diffusion agents. We assert that for PSA, which signifies the existence of a transnational network of actors, the significant diffusion agent is an exogenous actor whereas, for NPA, it would be an endogenous actor as it places importance on the role of the national policy networks.

For the purpose of this paper, exogenous diffusion agents are notably multilateral institutions such as the development banks namely the World Bank, the New Development Bank, the African Development Bank, and other multilateral institutions like the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Trade Organization (WTO), which disseminate ideas and practices by either making conditional financial loans or in the form of technical assistance through their teams of international consultants operating across the globe. For example, the electricity regulator in India and the water regulator in the State of Maharashtra in India were set up based on the terms and conditions of the World Bank loan. The financial and technical assistance brought with itself a foreign institution (considered as a best-practice measure) and a team of consultants to implant the institution.

Endogenous diffusion agents consist of the national community of policymakers, such as bureaucrats, politicians or civil society groups, which after learning from the outside experiences introduce changes in their own countries. For example, regulatory institutions in securities and telecom sector in namely, Securities & Exchange Board of India (SEBI) and Telecom Regulatory Authority of India (TRAI), were set up by legislators in India learning from structural reforms taken elsewhere in the world.

Table 1: Exogenous and Endogenous Agents and their characteristics

Exogenous Agents	Endogenous Agents
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multilateral and developmental institutions such as the World Bank and the IMF • Conditionalities imposed during technical and financial assistance induce change • Isomorphic transplantation of a standard model 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National actors such as policymakers and civil society • Changes induced after learning from structural reforms in other countries and sectors

2.2 Institutional change & Regulatory Arrangements

As mentioned earlier, the post-1991 crisis India embraced a neoliberal model for economic development. This paradigm shift also brought about changes in institutional governance. The ideals of New Public Management (NPM) where the role of the state would be to steer the economy instead of rowing started gaining momentum. The state started separating the rulemaking and service delivery functions. Interestingly IRAs were adopted as a preferred mode of regulation, notwithstanding the nature of diffusion agents and transfer channels. However, the reports of the Planning Commission of India and ARC recognized the absence of a common regulatory philosophy. While highlighting the divergences, the Planning Commission report states that the electricity regulators enjoy extensive powers vis-a-vis their peers.

To better understand the arguments going forward, we briefly illustrate how the reform process happened in a few of the sectors (which are also considered in this paper).

The reforms in the different sectors were undertaken at different points in time: securities market (1992), telecommunications (1997), electricity (1998), and aviation (2008). The securities market in India was controlled by the Controller of Capital Issues (CCI), which was established in 1947. The CCI controlled access to the equity market and would determine the

timing, price, and volume of primary equity to be issued. In a way, it became a market restrictor (Bhattacharya and Patel 2005). The role of the CCI came into conflict with the new economic philosophy of India after the economic reforms of 1991. As a result, the Government of India established a new independent regulator and abolished the CCI.

Reforms in the telecommunications sector were driven by political and bureaucratic elites. Realizing the monopoly of government over rulemaking, regulation and service delivery was unyielding. In order to facilitate private investment and promote competition, the regulatory role was taken away from the incumbent public-sector operator and was vested with an independent regulator (Mukherji 2006, 2009, 2014). Multilateral institutions, especially the World Bank, have been aiding the Indian electricity sector since the 1970s. Over time, they learned that the assistance was not creating a sustainable outcome; as a result, they calibrated their strategy and made further assistance conditional upon structural adjustments. One of the conditionality was to establish an IRA to depoliticize tariff setting. As a result, between 1996 and 1998, structural adjustment was undertaken across the country assisted by the World Bank's consultants, and IRAs were established for the sector (Précis 2001).

The aviation industry in India is primarily governed by the Ministry of Civil Aviation (MoCA) and Directorate General of Civil Aviation (DGCA) (an autonomous regulator) established by the Aircraft Act, 1934. As the operational activities grew in India, Government of India established Airports Authority of India (AAI²) in 1994, which came to be the operator and regulator of civil airports in India. DGCA³ was handed responsibility related to licensing, safety, and technical aspects. The debate from the 14th Lok Sabha (Lower House of Parliament) dated 22nd October 2008 when the bill creating Airports Economic Regulatory Authority of India (AERA) was passed, suggests that the Government of India created an independent economic regulator (with limited mandated of tariff determination of major airports) to provide a level playing in order to attract private investment for developing airports and separate the operational and regulatory functions of AAI.

² AAI was established after merging International Airports Authority of India (IAAI) and National Airports Authority (NAA) which were constituted in 1971 and 1985 to manage international and domestic airports, respectively, in India. The merger was considered necessary in order to promote better operational integration and financial management (AAI Act, 1994)

³ DGCA along with BCAS (Bureau of Civil Aviation Security) handles the security of civil flights

The reform process indicates institutional change across all sectors as separate IRAs were created. Yet, divergences are highlighted by the government reports. James Mahoney & Kathleen Thelen (2010), in their theory of gradual institutional change, state that the type of dominant change agent has an impact on the type of institutional change that takes place. Based on locus of institutional transformation, they delineated four modes of institutional change: (1) 'displacement' (the removal of existing rules and the introduction of new ones); (2) 'layering' (the introduction of new rules on top of or alongside existing ones); (3) "drift" (the changed impact of existing rules due to shifts in the environment); and 'conversion' (the changed enactment of existing rules due to their strategic redeployment) (Mahoney and Thelen 2010). For this study, we rely only on 'displacement' and 'layering' as the literature identifies the creation of a new organization within the pre-existing constellation of actors rather than changes to existing ones. .

After the reforms, IRA was embedded in an existing macrostructure that Mathieu et al. (2016) refer to as "regulatory arrangement," which represents the existing sectoral configuration that regulates the sector and is an outcome of institutional change. The asymmetrical dispersion of power and influence among the actors generates different kinds of regulatory arrangements. The literature identifies four possible types of regulatory arrangements: (1) 'concentrated' (concentration of decision-making influence in one actor, and other actors have little or no involvement); (2) 'consultative' (concentration of decision-making influence in one actor but other actors are also consulted); (3) 'cooperative' (none of the regulatory actors have more influence than the others); (4) 'fragmented' (dispersion of influence as several regulatory actors make specific regulatory decisions separately) (González 2017).

Based on our review, we suggest that there is a correlation between the influence of an actor in a regulatory arrangement and the nature of the agent in the diffusion process. We posit the following hypotheses:

H1: If an exogenous agent is the dominant vector in a diffusion process, then it will induce institutional displacement and in the resultant regulatory arrangement, the most influential actor will be the IRA.

H2: If an endogenous agent is a dominant vector in the diffusion process, then it will induce institutional layering and in the resultant regulatory arrangement, the most influential actor will not be the IRA.

Fig 1: Diagrammatic representation of the proposed hypotheses

3. Methodology

To investigate types of regulatory arrangements, we construct an actor influence index, a concentration index, and a coordination index. The Actor Influence Index measures how many regulatory issues an actor can influence and their degree of formal influence. The form of participation has broadly been coded into six categories (Table 2) and based on the same scores are awarded to the actors. This measure can be calculated by summing up the number of decisions in which the actor has any form of participation and dividing this sum by the total number of regulatory issues in a sector (Mathieu et al. 2016).

Table 2: Scale for the measurement of actors' influence in individual decisions

Weight	Coding	Description
0	Not involved	The actor is not involved in the decision
0.2	Informed	The actor is informed about the planned content of the decision
0.4	Consulted	The actor is consulted or gives non-binding advice
0.6	Binding Position	The actor makes a binding opinion or initiates the decision proposal
0.8	Co-decisionmaker	The actor is a co-decisionmaker
1.0	Main decisionmaker	The actor is the main decisionmaker

Source: (Mathieu et al. 2016)

The actor influence index is useful to compare actors within the sector; however, across sectors, this index is not directly comparable because the number of regulatory responsibilities differs (or may differ) from sector to sector. This problem can be alleviated by computing the concentration index, which provides a standardized measurement on a scale of 0 to 1 as shown in Table 2 above. The concentration index measures the concentration of influence in actors in a regulatory arrangement. The idea is to assess the degree of asymmetry in influence.

The coordination index measures interaction among the actors involved in the decision-making procedure. The actor influence index measures how many regulatory issues an actor can influence, which in turn indicates that every actor has a different level of influence across various issues. On some issues, one actor might be the main decision-maker, whereas on other issues, its influence may be restricted to providing non-binding recommendations. Similarly, the influence of all the actors in decision-making will vary as per table 2.

Once the concentration and coordination indexes are calculated (a detailed explanation on how calculation has been done is given in Annexure D), the type of regulatory arrangement can be determined as per the classification provided by the González (2017) and shown below:

Fig 2: Types of Regulatory Arrangements (Source: González 2017)

3.2 Selection of Sectors

The selection of sectors analyzed was driven by the following factors:

- a) Presence of an Independent Regulatory Agency (IRA).

b) As the administrative framework in India is multi-level in nature with the division of legislative functions into Union List, State List, and Concurrent List, sectors were selected in order to represent each of the lists⁴.

c) Institutional reforms were driven by either exogenous or endogenous diffusion agents.

Hence, the sectors analyzed in this study are:

Table 3: Sectors and diffusion agents

Sl.	Sector	Legislative list	Diffusion agent (as identified from literature)
1.	Securities Market	Union	Endogenous
2.	Electricity	Concurrent	Exogenous
3.	Telecommunications	Union	Endogenous
4.	Aviation	Union	Endogenous
5.	Groundwater (Maharashtra)	State	Exogenous
6.	Groundwater (Uttar Pradesh)	State	Endogenous

3.3 Data collection and coding

We explore the formal regulatory arrangements of the sectors by identifying the formal distribution of regulatory responsibility⁵ and then by locating what influence actors have in those identified regulatory responsibilities. Data collection was undertaken using the current national sector-specific primary legislations. Securities Contracts (Regulation) Act, 1956, The Indian Telegraph Act, 1885, Electricity Act, 2003, The Aircraft Act, 1934, Maharashtra Groundwater (Development and Management) Act, 2013 and Uttar Pradesh Groundwater (Management and Regulation) Bill⁶, 2017 are the primary statutes that respectively govern the

⁴ Refer Annexure C at the end for details on legislative divisions

⁵, which can be understood as the formal allocation or delegation of policy or regulatory issues by or to actors (involved in the regulatory arrangement of field) to elaborate regulations or make decisions based on the legal framework governing the sector.

⁶ The State legislature of Uttar Pradesh is yet to enact the groundwater regulation. As of now, the legislation is in the form of a bill and not an act. However, it adds to the analysis when studied in conjunction with the groundwater act of the Maharashtra State.

securities, telecommunications, electricity, aviation, and groundwater sectors in India (two states in the case of groundwater). After screening the primary legislation, regulatory responsibilities were identified and, in accordance with table 1, scores were awarded to the actors based on their involvement in the decision-making process. For example, for two different issues in the electricity sector, scoring was done as follows. As the framing of tariff regulations is the sole prerogative of IRAs as per Electricity Act, 2003, a score of 1 was awarded to the IRAs. In the process of awarding the license, regulators have to give an opportunity to the public and other involved actors to raise objections or suggestions that are non-binding on the regulator. Thus, a score of 1 was awarded to the CERC (national regulator) and the SERCs (state-level regulators), and the rest of the actors were awarded 0.4 as they were consulted, but their advice is of non-binding nature.

Whenever regulatory issues were not dealt with in primary legislation or allocation of responsibility was ambiguous, secondary legislation and information (e.g., agency websites) were considered. For instance, The Indian Telegraph Act, 1885 dates back to the colonial era and it explicitly mentions that tariff has to be decided by the central government. However, wireline telephony has become obsolete, there exists competition in the wireless domain and an IRA was established to regulate the sector. Therefore, after reading the primary legislation (The Indian Telegraph Act, 1885) in consonance with secondary legislation of the sector (The Telecommunications Regulatory Authority Act of India, 1997) one can find that the central government is not involved in tariff setting and it is the sectoral regulator's responsibility to regulate tariff matters (for which it issues rules and regulations). Thus, the only institution to be awarded a score of 1 is the regulator. The framing of tariff regulations is the sole prerogative of IRAs per Electricity Act of 2003, and a score of 1 was awarded to IRAs. However, as per the established procedure mentioned in the secondary legislation, the IRAs ask stakeholders for non-binding suggestions. As before, the IRAs were awarded a score of 1 and the other actors were awarded a score of 0.4.

Identifying regulatory responsibilities and awarding the scores allowed us to calculate the actor influence index and concentration index. The results can be interpreted in terms of the influence of all involved actors, including IRAs, in the regulatory arrangement.

4. Findings

Table 3 presents the actor influence index, concentration index, and coordination index for the six sectors.

4.1 Actor Influence Index

Table 4 suggests that each of these sectors has one actor who influences the most number of regulatory issues compared to any other actors in their respective sectors. However, the nature of the most influential actor in these sectors are different. While in the case of groundwater (Maharashtra), electricity, and securities sector it is the sectoral IRA that has more formal influence, for telecommunications, it is the line ministry, for aviation its the autonomous regulator embedded within the ministry, and for groundwater (Uttar Pradesh) it is a council of body (District Council) headed by district magistrate (a bureaucrat who is chief executive of a district⁷).

4.2 Concentration Index

The concentration index of groundwater (Maharashtra) is highest among the six sectors, followed closely by electricity and aviation sector, which means the concentration of influence (the degree of asymmetry) between the influence of the most influential actor of the arrangement and the influence of the remaining actors, is the highest in the groundwater (Maharashtra) sector, followed by electricity and aviation sectors. This is evident in Table 4 as well where MWRRA, SERC, and DGCA have an influence score of 0.72, 0.57, and 0.60 which is much higher than the influence score of any other actors in their respective sectors.

Even though the influence score of the most influential actor in groundwater (Uttar Pradesh) (DGWMC), telecommunications (DoT), and securities (SEBI) sector is in proximity to that of the electricity (SERC) and aviation (DGCA) sectors, the concentration index in these three sectors is significantly lower, with groundwater (Uttar Pradesh) being the lowest at 0.24. This signifies that the influence score of other actors involved in these sectors is also on the higher side. This, in turn, signifies two possibilities. Either similar regulatory responsibilities are formally distributed between two or more actors with final authority being vested in the most

⁷ An administrative division of the second level. India constitutes of 7 Union territories and 29 States. For administrative purposes, each state is further divided into districts.

influential actor, or responsibilities are distributed in a manner that there are no overlaps, and each actor has exclusive jurisdiction on the allocated responsibility.

4.3 Coordination Index

The coordination index is highest for the electricity sector (0.33) which suggests that vis-a-vis other sectors there is more interaction between actors in the decision-making process. The scores for groundwater (Uttar Pradesh and Maharashtra) and telecommunications (0.26, 0.23, and 0.17) suggest that fewer actors in these sectors interact in the decision-making process. At the other end of the spectrum is the aviation sector, where no actors interact in decision-making; in the securities sector, there is also very little interaction

Table 4: Actor Influence score and Concentration Index of sectors

Securities			Telecommunications			Electricity*		
Actors	Nature of actor	Actor Influence Index	Actors	Nature of actor	Actor Influence Index	Actors	Nature of actor	Actor Influence Index
SEBI	IRA	0.58	DoT	Ministry	0.59	SERCs	IRA	0.57
Central Government	Government of India	0.25	TRAI	IRA	0.44	CERC ⁸	IRA	0.20
Stock Exchanges		0.25	USOFA	Ministry	0.13	CEA	Technical Authority	0.17
						Distribution Licensee	Utility	0.13
Concentration Index for sectors								
Securities = 0.33			Telecom = 0.32			Electricity = 0.49		
Coordination Index for sectors								
Securities = 0.04			Telecom = 0.17			Electricity = 0.33		

*7 more actors with score of 0.07 and less not shown here due to low magnitude of influence score

⁸ Both CERC and SERCs are sectoral regulators. CERC is a central regulator that mainly regulates public sector generating companies owned by the central government, the intra-state transmission of electricity, and any other matter involving the central and state government or two or more state governments. SERCs are state-level agencies that regulate generation, transmission, distribution, and other issues at the state (sub-national) level. As the number of issues to be regulated at the state level is higher (especially due to distribution-related matters), the role of state-level regulators stands out compared to the central regulator.

Table 4: Actor Influence score and Concentration Index of sectors

Aviation			Groundwater (Maharashtra)			Groundwater (Uttar Pradesh)		
Actors	Nature of actor	Actor Influence Index	Actors	Nature of actor	Actor Influence Index	Actors	Nature of actor	Actor Influence Index
DGCA	Autonomous regulator ⁹	0.60	MWRRA	IRA	0.72	DGWMC	Public unit @ district level	0.55
MoCA	Ministry	0.16	GoM/GSDA ¹⁰	State Government	0.39	MWMC	Public unit for Urban areas	0.40
AERA	IRA	0.13	WWRC	Committee	0.17	GoUP/GWD ¹¹	State Government	0.31
BCAS	Autonomous regulator	0.10	District Authority	Bureaucrat	0.15	GPGWSC	Public unit for rural areas	0.31
			Panchayat	Local self-government	0.10	BPGWMC	Public unit @ block level	0.28
			CGWA	Central Government	0.03	State Council (SGWMRC)	Regulatory council	0.24
Concentration Index for sectors								
Aviation = 0.17			Groundwater (Maharashtra) = 0.55			Groundwater (Uttar Pradesh) = 0.24		
Coordination Index for sectors								
Aviation = 0.00			Groundwater (Maharashtra) = 0.23			Groundwater (Uttar Pradesh) = 0.26		

⁹ Embedded in line ministry and deals with safety issues

¹⁰ GSDA is a department under the Water Ministry of Government of Maharashtra (GoM). Hence, they have been grouped together

¹¹ GWD is a department under the Water Ministry of the Government of Uttar Pradesh (GoUP). Hence, they have been clubbed together

5. Discussion of findings

5.1 Types of regulatory arrangement

In this section, we examine the diversity of the regulatory arrangements of six sectors where IRAs exist, as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Type of Regulatory Arrangements

All six sectors can be classified between concentrated and fragmented regulatory arrangements. Whereas securities, telecommunications, aviation and groundwater (UP) can be classified as having a fragmented regulatory arrangement, electricity, and groundwater (MH) have concentrated regulatory arrangements.

A challenge is whether to undertake a strict classification of sectors into fragmented and concentrated regulatory arrangements and ignore the interaction among actors (however little they might be).

As per the definition provided by González, in fragmented regulatory arrangements, there is no interaction between actors in the decision-making process. However, from Figure 1, we observe interaction among actors in all sectors, except aviation, but at varying degrees. The low coordination score suggests that out of all actors involved in a sector, only few interact on every

issue. Therefore, it would be prudent to consider sectors such as telecommunications, electricity, and groundwater (MH) as having elements of a consultative type of regulatory arrangement (though there is no strict threshold to decide above what score it should be considered).

Table 5: Summary of findings

Sl.	Sector	Type of Regulatory Arrangement
1.	Securities Market ¹²	Fragmented
2.	Telecommunications	Fragmented-consultative
3.	Electricity	Concentrated-consultative
4.	Aviation	Fragmented
5.	Groundwater (Maharashtra)	Concentrated-consultative
6.	Groundwater (Uttar Pradesh)	Fragmented

5.2 Agents of diffusion and regulatory arrangement

In this section, we try to answer the second part of the research question and test our hypothesis by exploring the relationship between the nature of diffusion agents (exogenous or endogenous) and resultant formal regulatory arrangement. We keep in mind that the traditional administrative model of governance in India is hierarchical in nature. The line ministries would govern the sectors through various departments that would have attached and subordinate offices (Moily et al. 2009). The reforms initiated post-1991 aimed at restructuring the governance model in these sectors.

The key characteristic of an IRA, as provided by the World Bank handbook, is independence in decision making. As the principal reason for creating IRAs is to depoliticize tariff setting and other regulatory decisions, the agency should be able to make a decision without prior approval of the government, and such decisions can only be overruled by the judiciary or any other appellate authority. For a regulatory agency to be independent, it should have organizational independence (separated from existing ministries and departments), fiscal independence (an earmarked, secure, and adequate source of funding), and management

¹² In the securities sector, there is only one issue on which there is an interaction between two actors. Due to a very low score, its interaction was not considered.

independence (autonomy over internal administration and protection from dismissal without due cause) (Brown et al. 2006).

Table 6: Type of regulatory arrangement and diffusion agents

Sl.	Sector	Type of Regulatory Arrangement	Influential Actor (and nature of actor)	Diffusion agent
1.	Securities Market	Fragmented	SEBI (IRA)	Endogenous
2.	Telecommunications	Fragmented-consultative	DoT (Ministry)	Endogenous
3.	Electricity	Concentrated-consultative	SERCs (IRA)	Exogenous
4.	Aviation	Fragmented	DGCA (Autonomous regulator)	Endogenous
5.	Groundwater (Maharashtra)	Concentrated-consultative	MWRRA (IRA)	Exogenous
6.	Groundwater (Uttar Pradesh)	Fragmented	DGWMC (Public unit)	Endogenous

Tables 2, 3, and 5 identify the diffusion agents, the actor influence index, and the regulatory arrangements for each sector. To answer the second part of the research question, our findings are further summarized in Table 6.

The diffusion agents are 'exogenous' in the electricity and groundwater (MH) sectors, and IRAs are the most influential actor in both. In remaining four sectors (securities, telecommunications, aviation, and groundwater (UP)), the diffusion agents are 'endogenous' and most influential actor is not an IRA, (except for securities sector). These results confirm our hypothesis that there appears to be a relationship between the type of diffusion agent and the nature of the most influential actor in a regulatory arrangement. The outlier is the securities sector, and a plausible reason could be the sector's peculiarity. Unlike the utilities and infrastructure sector, which are monopolistic and subject to domestic political pressure (due to the presence of the public-sector unit or politicization), that is not the situation in the securities market.

To explore whether diffusion agents are associated with institutional change, we delve into the reform process in the sectors (except for securities). Mukherji (2014) noted that when the Government of India established the telecommunications regulator (TRAI), it did not abolish the existing institutional body, the Department of Telecom (DoT), which had sole authority over policymaking, regulatory functions, and service delivery. Instead, powers and functions were re-allocated between DoT and TRAI, and DoT continues to be the most influential actor.

According to him this type of institutional change was 'layering' in nature as a new actor was woven around the existing one.

In the electricity sector, it is well-documented that the institutional change introduced was contrary to existing administrative tradition. Dubash & Rajan's (2001) analysis of reform in power sector concluded that the introduction of IRAs happened through the backdoor. The new institutional experiment, which broke away from the hierarchical model and introduced an independent regulator, was not tested through national politics. Even the World Bank's report, Précis (2001), highlights how in line with their philosophy of depoliticization of sector, structural change was needed. Existing rules were displaced and new ones were established amounting to institutional displacement in the sector.

Reforms in the aviation sector are a classic example of a 'credible commitment' argument, which states that when the government pushes privatization and liberalization reforms, it creates an independent regulator to bind itself to the policy decision, giving necessary safeguards to investors (Gilardi 2004). From our analysis, we can infer that the creation of an independent regulator for aviation (AERA), was very similar to the philosophy followed for the telecommunications sector, which was to separate service delivery and regulatory functions of the incumbent (AAI). The IRA was created but with a limited mandate to determine tariffs only for major airports. The incumbent actor (DGCA, an autonomous regulator embedded in the ministry) continues to be the most influential actor in the sector.

Maharashtra Water Resource Regulatory Authority (MWRRA) was established as an independent water regulator in the Indian state of Maharashtra in 2005 in pursuance of reform agenda driven by the World Bank. Following its establishment, it became a model institution for water resource regulation in India and was adopted by six other states (Warghade 2016). The World Bank has been provided further assistance in the area of groundwater in the State of Maharashtra under the Rural Water Supply and Sanitation Project (World Bank, 2010). It is no coincidence that an IRA is the most influential actor in the regulation of groundwater, which prior to reforms was regulated by a government department. The World Bank's toolkit for private-sector participation in water services emphasizes consultation and consensus-building with stakeholders, which explains the substantial influence of other actors as well in the regulatory arrangement (World Bank, 2006; Dubash and Morgan 2013). This new kind of institutional arrangement is vastly different from the hierarchical model. Therefore, in this sector too, there has been an institutional displacement.

In the State of Uttar Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh Water Management and Regulatory Commission (UPWMRC) was established in 2008 on the lines of MWRRRA, as stated above. However, it remained an authority on paper only and never became operational (Koonan and Bhullar 2012). Even though the World Bank provides assistance to the State of Uttar Pradesh in the area of groundwater, the proposed regulatory model is based on the model groundwater management bill of the Central Government of India, which does not specifically require the establishment of an IRA for groundwater. For the time being, as the proposed reform in the State of Uttar Pradesh is based on the model bill of the Government of India; it can be said to be endogenously driven where maximum influence has been proposed to be vested in an institution that is neither an IRA or an incumbent. It is organized as a council comprised of representation from various departments of state government, instead of one department, thereby pointing towards another instance of institutional layering.

These findings confirm our hypothesis that there appears to be correlation between the nature of the diffusion agent, the mode of institutional change, and the influence of IRAs in the resultant formal regulatory arrangement in the infrastructure sectors. The outlier to this scenario is the securities sector, which calls for more research on the factors influencing financial regulation.

6. Conclusions

This paper puts together two different theories, i.e. Jordana. Levi-Faur & Marin's channels of institutional transfer and Mahoney & Thelen's gradual institutional change, to help identify reasons for variable influence of IRAs within the formal regulatory arrangements. The regulatory agencies, namely the IRAs, were considered a best-practice measure to help alleviate the governance issues, especially in the developing economies where existing institutional arrangements were proving to be a hindrance to attracting capital investment, specifically for infrastructure projects. However, IRAs began operating in a space where there was a pre-existing institutional set-up and it is necessary to analyze them in this context.

Before undertaking any major reforms across sectors, the existing dynamics at both the micro and macro levels should be understood, especially if the objective is to converge regulatory philosophy. By analyzing formal regulatory arrangements and the influence of IRAs, this study contributes toward building this understanding. It shows how isolated and piecemeal reforms initiated by different diffusion agents contributed to existing divergences. In four sectors

(securities, telecommunications, aviation, and groundwater (UP)), reforms were led by endogenous diffusion agents. In the electricity and groundwater (MH) sectors, reforms were driven by the exogenous actors. As a result there is variation in the formal regulatory arrangements and influence of IRAs in the sectors. The results of the study find a correlation between nature of diffusion agent and variable influence of IRAs within the regulatory arrangement. However, the non-conformity of securities sector to the results suggest importance of sectoral peculiarity in explaining variations in influence of IRAs.

The ongoing discussions around regulatory reform suggests that policymakers are deliberating convergence in India's regulatory philosophy. Due to the multilevel governance framework, sectors are regulated either by the central government (securities, telecommunications, aviation), state government (groundwater) or concurrently by the central and state government (electricity). In such scenario, there is a possibility that reforms could be driven either by the central or state government. This dichotomy could very well play out the way the dichotomy of 'exogenous' and 'endogenous' diffusion agent has. Therefore, inferring from this study, it would also be wise to deliberate upon who should be the driver of reforms going forward. In the regulatory space, resources are fragmented among the institutions involved, including the regulator, regulated industries, the state, and non-state actors (such as civil society organizations) (Hancher and Moran 1998; Scott 2001). When resources and power are dispersed among actors, so will be their influence. To understand how regulatory governance functions on the ground level, it is important to examine the nature and extent of influence that institutions exercise over each other. However, to understand such de facto dispersion of influence (which in turn will enrich the understanding of policy diffusion), a point of reference is needed with regard to the formal dispersion of power among actors. Hence, analyzing the design of regulatory governance and arrangements matters. A limitation of this study is that it only measures the formal dimensions of regulatory arrangements, but it provides a basis for exploring de facto arrangements in future research. Comparing the evolution of both formal and de facto regulatory arrangements and their effectiveness could provide interesting insights about regulatory governance globally and common institutional challenges.

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Annexure A – List of Abbreviations for Table 4

1. Electricity sector	
SERC	State Electricity Regulatory Commission
CERC	Central Electricity Regulatory Commission
CEA	Central Electricity Authority
2. Telecom sector	
DoT	Department of Telecom
TRAI	Telecom Regulatory Authority of India
USOFA	Universal Service Obligation Fund Administrator
3. Aviation Sector	
DGCA	Directorate General of Civil Aviation
MoCA	Ministry of Civil Aviation
AERA	Airports Economic Regulatory Authority
BCAS	Bureau of Civil Aviation Security
4. Securities sector	
SEBI	Securities and Exchange Board of India
5. Groundwater (Maharashtra)	
MWRRA	Maharashtra Water Resources Regulatory Authority
GoM	Government of Maharashtra
GSDA	Groundwater Surveys and Development Agency
WWRC	Watershed Water Resources Committee
CGWA	Central Ground Water Authority
6. Groundwater (Uttar Pradesh)	
DGWMC	District Ground Water Management Council
MWMC	Municipal Water Management Committee
GoUP	Government of Uttar Pradesh
GWD	Ground Water Department
GPGWSC	Gram Panchayat Ground Water Sub-Committee
BPGWMC	Block Panchayat Ground Water Management Committee
SGWMRC	State Ground Water Management and Regulatory Council

Annexure B

Administrative framework in India

The Constitution of India in Article 1 states that India shall be Union of States. Despite using the word 'Union of States' to describe the character of Indian state, the governance framework in India is not unitary. Alexandrowicz in his analysis, whether India is a federation or not, has stated that strictly looking through the rigid federal principles, India cannot be classified as a federal state. Instead the exponents of federal principle such as K.C. Wheare have classified India as a quasi-federal state (Alexandrowicz, 2017). Even the Supreme Court of India, which has exclusive powers with respect to interpreting the Constitution, in numerous judgments (State of West Bengal vs. Union of India in 1964; State of Rajasthan vs. Union of India in 1978; State of Karnataka vs. Union of India in 1977 etc.) has characterized India as a quasi-federal state. Though India is a not a true federal state, there is division of power between the national and sub-national governments (henceforth referred to as Central government and State government respectively) which creates a multi-level governance framework.

In the multi-level governance framework of India there is a division of legislative functions between the Central and the State government. The Constitution of India (Part XI and Schedule VII) provides for three lists, namely, Union List, State List and Concurrent List which specifies who can make laws on which subject. In Part XI (which deals with legislative relations between the Union and the State) under Article 246 of the Constitution of India, the Central and the State government has exclusive power to legislate on matters enumerated in the Union List and State List, respectively. With respect to the Concurrent List both, the Central and the State government can enact laws, however in case there is an inconsistency between the laws made by the Central and the State government then to that extent of inconsistency, the law enacted by the former will prevail over the latter (Article 254 of the Constitution of India).

The division of legislative functions between the Central and State government can be better understood from the following illustrations. Posts and telegraphs (telephones, wireless, broadcasting and other like forms of communication) can be found in the Union List (entry 31 of the Union List). As the Central government has sole prerogative of making laws for items placed in the Union List, the telecom sector is regulated pan-India by the policies, laws, departments and agencies controlled by the Central government. Aviation, Banking, Insurance, Stock exchange & futures market etc. are examples of other items which can be found in the Union List (and where IRAs exist)

Water as an item can be found in both, the Union List (entry 56) and the State List (entry 17). However, it is the respective State governments who have the authority to formulate policies related to water supplies, irrigation, storage etc. The Central government usually assists with inter-state distribution of water. As the role of the State governments is central with respect to legislation of water sector, each State government enacts its own laws for regulating the water sector in their respective jurisdictions. The variations between state laws can be observed from the fact that out of 29 states, only 6 states have established an IRA for the water sector. This re-affirms exclusive power of each State government to make laws with respect to the items placed in the State List.

Electricity as an item can be found as an entry 38 in the Concurrent List where both the Central and the State government have the power to enact laws. In this instance the Central government has framed a national legislation which provides a framework for regulating the sector across the country and in accordance with the same each State government has enacted its own laws to regulate electricity sector in its jurisdiction. As Kale aptly puts it, the principle responsibility of Central government is to frame laws and that of State government is to implement them (Kale 2004). Further, the Central government has created Central Electricity Regulatory Commission (CERC) which governs inter-state generation and transmission of electricity. Each State government has created their own State Electricity Regulatory Commission (SERC) which regulates intra-state generation, transmission and distribution¹³ of electricity.

¹³ Distribution of electricity is under the exclusive jurisdiction of each State government.

Annexure C

List of Primary and Secondary Legislations considered

S. No.	Sector	Primary Legislation	Secondary Legislation
1.	Electricity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electricity Act, 2003 along with amendments issued in 2007 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MERC (Conduct of Business) Regulations, 2004
2.	Telecommunication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Indian Telegraph Act, 1885 along with amendments issued in 1957, 1971 & 2003 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Telecom Regulatory Authority Act of India, 1997 along with amendments issued in 2000 & 2014 Indian Telegraph (Amendment) Rules, 2004 The Indian Wireless Telegraphy Act, 1993
3.	Aviation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Aircraft Act, 1934 along with amendments issued in 1936, 1938, 1939, 1944, 1948, 1960, 1972, 1983, 1985, 1988, 2000, 2007 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Airports Authority of India Act, 1994 along with amendment issued in 2003 The Airports Economic Regulatory Authority of India Act, 2008 along with amendment issued in 2019 Aircraft Rules, 1937 Aircraft Security Rules, 2011
4.	Securities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Securities Contracts (Regulation) Act, 1956 along with amendments issued in 1995, 1999, 2004 	<ul style="list-style-type: none">
5.	Groundwater MH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maharashtra Groundwater (Development & Management) Act, 2009 	<ul style="list-style-type: none">

6.	Groundwater UP	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The Uttar Pradesh Ground Water (Management and Regulation) Bill, 2017	
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Annexure D

Equations used in calculation of indices: Source (Mathieu et. al 2016)

Equations	Variables	Description
$C_o = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^i a_j - 1}{i(a - 1)}$	a	Number of actors in the regulatory arrangement
	i	Number of issues in the regulatory arrangement
	Co	Coordination Index
$AI(A_k) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^i AI(A_k I_j)}{i}$	aj	Number of actors involved in the decision over the issue number j
	AI	Actor Influence Index
	AI(AK)	Actor Influence of Actor number k on the whole regulatory arrangement
$C_c = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^i [AI(A_{max}) - AI(A_k)]}{a - 1}$	AI(AkIj)	Actor Influence of Actor number k on the issue number j
	Cc	Concentration Index
	AI(Amax)	Actor Influence of most influent actor of the regulatory arrangement

The actor influence index is useful to compare actors within the sector; however, across sectors, this index is not directly comparable because the number of regulatory responsibilities differs (or may differ) from sector to sector. For example, assuming the number of regulatory responsibilities in electricity, telecommunications, and aviation sectors are 30, 20, and 10 respectively. Each of these sectors has three players, say, 'A', 'B' and 'C'. To calculate the actor influence index of actors 'A', 'B', 'C' in the electricity sector, the sum of scores (ranging from 0 to 1) awarded to them based on their involvement in decision-making on all issues would be divided by 30. Similarly, for the actors 'A', 'B' and 'C' in telecom and aviation sectors, the actor influence index would be calculated by dividing individual scores of each actor by 20 and 10 respectively. Since the denominator in each of the instances is not the same, these actors cannot

be compared across sectors. To overcome this problem we calculate concentration index, which provides a standardized measurement on a scale of 0 to 1.

To compute the concentration index, it is first necessary to compute the concentration score, which is the summation of the difference between the actor influence index of the most influential actor and that of the other actors. For example, we assume a scenario wherein any particular sector, the actor influence index of actors 'A', 'B' and 'C' are 0.60, 0.45 and 0.20 respectively. To calculate the concentration score, it is necessary to first subtract from the actor influence index of A, actor influence index of B and C individually ($0.60 - 0.45 = 0.15$) and ($0.60 - 0.20 = 0.40$). Adding results of A-B and A-C ($0.15 + 0.40$) results in a value of 0.55 (also calculated as $0.60 \times 2 - (0.45 + 0.20)$).

Like the actor influence index, the concentration score also is not a standardized measurement and concentration scores of two or more sectors are not comparable. The standardization of influence on a scale of 0 to 1 (to facilitate comparison) is done by calculating the Concentration Index. The concentration index of 0 indicates that influence is equally distributed among involved actors, whereas 1 indicates there is only one influential actor in the sector. Continuing with the above example, the maximum difference between the influence of actors would be reached when the influence of 'A' is 1 and that of 'B' and 'C' is 0. In such a scenario, the concentration score of the sector would be $2 \{ [1 \times 2 - (0 + 0)] \}$ i.e., the total number of actors in arrangement minus one. To calculate the concentration index, we divide the concentration score by the total number of actors in the arrangement minus one. In the above example, where the concentration score is 0.55 and the number of actors in the arrangement is three, the concentration index would be 0.55 divided by 2 (0.27).

The coordination index measures interaction among the actors involved in the decision-making procedure. This index is calculated first by adding up all the number of actors that interact in each decision which will give coordination score. To allow comparability, the coordination score is transformed to a scale of 0 to 1. The minimal value of coordination score would be achieved when only one actor takes all decisions without the involvement of others. The maximum value would be achieved when all actors interact on all issues. If in a sector 'a₁, a₂...a₅' are actors and 'i' are issues, then the minimum value of the coordination score would be reached when only a₁ takes decisions on all issues i.e. (a₁ x i). The maximum value of the coordination score would be reached when all five actors are involved in all issues, i.e., ((a₁, a₂...a₅) x i).

To standardize on a scale of 0 to 1, the minimum value of the coordination index should become 0 and the maximum value should become 1. To do so, from the absolute coordination score its minimal value should be subtracted. The resultant number is divided by the difference between the maximum and minimum value.